

through oxygen and nitrogen to metal ions is further indicated by the appearance of ν_{M-O} and ν_{M-N} at 440–455 and 610–625 cm^{-1} respectively. Thus, the Schiff bases behave as bifunctional tetradentate (ONNO donor) ligands^{9–11}. The presence of coordinated ν -picoline in the complexes is known from their $\nu_{C-C} + \nu_{C-N}$ bands found at 1 530–1 540 cm^{-1} . The other bands were masked by the Schiff base bands. In the compounds containing thiourea, the ν_{C-S} band shifted to lower frequency (710–720 cm^{-1}) indicating its coordination through sulphur atom¹². The shifting of ν_{N-O} band of pyridine-*N*-oxide from 1 265 to 1 205–1 215 cm^{-1} and δ_{N-O} band from 840 to 845–850 cm^{-1} indicate its bonding to the metal ions through the oxygen atom¹³.

The four Ni(SB)L compounds were found to exhibit absorption bands in the region 13 071–16 393 cm^{-1} which support a pentacoordinated geometry¹⁴. No absorption band for these compounds was found above 17 000 cm^{-1} . Absorption bands due to the two Ni(SB)L₂ compounds at 12 195–12 345, 15 598–15 748 and 25 974–26 315 cm^{-1} may be assigned to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively, for octahedral stereochemistry of divalent nickel¹⁵. The Cu(SB)L compounds were found to exhibit band at 16 129–16 260 cm^{-1} which supports the pentacoordinated stereochemistry^{16,17}. A broad band at 15 873 cm^{-1} for Cu(SB)L₂ complex indicates a distorted octahedral configuration^{18–20}. Bands due to the three manganese(II) compounds at 25 974–26 666, 22 470–23 809 and 17 543–17 699 cm^{-1} support octahedral configuration²¹. Thus, pentacoordinated Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} and hexacoordinated Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Mn^{II} compounds containing bifunctional tetradentate Schiff bases and neutral N, O or S donor ligands are reported.

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Transition Metal Complexes with 4-Amino-5-mercapto-3-methyl-1,2,4-triazole and 8-Hydroxyquinoline

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WE report here the syntheses and characterisation of a few mixed ligand complexes of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II} and VO^{II} with 4-amino-5-mercapto-3-methyl-1,2,4-triazole and 8-hydroxyquinoline. The complexes are expected to have potentialities as insecticides and pesticides.

Experimental

4-Amino-5-mercapto-3-methyl-1,2,4-triazole was prepared according to the literature method¹ by cyclisation of thiocarbohydrazide with glacial acetic acid.

A hot aqueous solution of the ligand (AMMT) (1 mmol) was added to an aqueous solution of the metal chloride (1 mmol) with constant stirring. To the resulting mixture, 8-hydroxyquinoline (1 mmol) in ethanol (55%) was added dropwise. The resulting coloured precipitates separated immediately, were kept on a water-bath for 30 min and filtered hot. The complexes were dried over fused calcium chloride (Table 1).

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 398 spectrophotometer and electronic (DMF) spectra on a Beckmann 35 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility was determined at room temperature by the Gouy method². Thermogravimetric analyses were carried out on a Netzsch 429 instrument at the rate of 10° min⁻¹ in air taking 100 mg of the sample. Conductivity was measured on a Toshniwal conductivity bridge and a dip type cell (cell constant=0.639, concentration of the solution 1 × 10⁻³ M in DMF).

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
			M	N	S
[Cu(AMMT)(HQ)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Bluish green	211	18.41 (18.50)	16.32 (16.35)	9.28 (9.34)
[Ni(AMMT)(HQ)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Green	>250	17.28 (17.40)	16.51 (16.56)	9.43 (9.46)
[Co(AMMT)(HQ)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Orange yellow	>250	17.86 (17.40)	16.89 (16.56)	9.37 (9.46)
[Mn(AMMT)(HQ)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow	>250	16.44 (16.40)	16.58 (16.76)	9.46 (9.50)
[VO(AMMT)(HQ)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Deep blue	>250	15.97 (15.40)	16.94 (16.96)	9.61 (9.96)

Results and Discussion

The complexes are insoluble in water and common organic solvents but are partially soluble in DMF. They are non-electrolytic in nature as revealed from the conductance data. Based on elemental analyses, the stoichiometry of the complexes have been computed to be [M(AMMT)(HQ)(H₂O)₂].

Though ligand 4-amino-5-mercapto-3-methyl-1,2,4-triazole (AMMT) in solution may exist either in the thione(I) or thiol(II) form, the ir spectra provide evidence of some thione form in solid state³. In the ir spectra of AMMT two bands at ~3 250 (NH₂) and 3 050 cm⁻¹ (NH) are observed.

The broad bands at 3 400–3 200 cm⁻¹ which is centered around 3 350 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the complexes, are due to ν_{OH} of coordinated water and ν_{NH} . The broadening may be attributed to intramolecular hydrogen bonding.

The weak ν_{SH} band at ~2 500 cm⁻¹ (ligand) is absent in the spectra of the metal complexes suggesting M–S bond formation. Positions of ligand bonds at ~1 570 (C=N) and 1 040 cm⁻¹ (N–N) remained unaltered in the spectra of the complexes suggesting non-participation of the ring nitrogen in coordination.

The ligand ν_{C-S} band at 745 cm⁻¹ disappeared and a new band at 660 cm⁻¹ (C–S) was observed in the complexes suggesting coordination of the enol form to metal with the loss of SH proton.

Charles *et al.*⁴ reported that for several metal complexes with oxine, the ν_{C-O} band is observed at ~1 120 cm⁻¹. The position of this band undergoes variation depending on the metal complex under study. In the present investigation, a strong band is observed at ~1 125 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of the oxine group in the complexes coordinating through its nitrogen and oxygen atoms as uninegative bidentate ligand.

The lower frequency region of the spectra of the complexes furnishes vital information regarding the mode of coordination of the ligands. The presence of M–N, M–O and M–S is evident from the bands appearing at ~470, 410 and 440 cm⁻¹ respectively⁵.

Thus the ligand AMMT provided bidentate (\bar{N} , \bar{S}) coordination to metal ions through amino nitrogen and thiol sulphur. The other ligand oxine coordinates through its nitrogen and oxygen.

The thermograms of the metal complexes follow similar pattern. The Cu^{II} complex starts losing weight around 170° with a weight-loss of 9.61% at 180° corresponding to the loss of two water molecules (9.66% theor.) in a single step supported by an endothermic peak at the same temperature in the DTA thermogram. This suggests that the two water molecules are coordinated to the metal ion in a similar chemical environment. The decomposition proceeds slowly above 180° and the final weight-loss becomes 21.32% at about 860° which corresponds to the formation of metal oxide. This thermal behaviour corresponds to the stoichiometry suggested for the complexes. The thermal stability of the complexes is in the order, Ni > Mn > Co > Cu.

The electronic spectrum of the Cu^{II} complex shows a broad asymmetric ligand field band in the region 14 000–17 000 cm⁻¹ with maxima at ~15 000 cm⁻¹ corresponding to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition in a nearly octahedral arrangement around copper(II) ion. The width and asymmetry of the band suggest tetragonal distortion and Jahn–Teller effect. The complex possesses magnetic moment of 2.03 B.M.

The spectrum of the Ni^{II} complex shows two bands at 16 940 and 27 770 cm⁻¹. In an octahedral approximation these bands can be assigned to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively. The magnetic moment value (2.95 B.M.) also confirms the octahedral stereochemistry around Ni^{II} ion. The nephelauxetic ratio (β) calculated for the Ni^{II} complex is 0.86 indicating partial covalency in the metal–ligand bond.

The Co^{II} complex possesses magnetic moment of 4.81 B.M. The electronic spectrum of the complex shows bands at ~15 030, 17 380 and 24 400 cm⁻¹.

The band at $\sim 15\,030\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ transition. The band at $\sim 17\,380\text{ cm}^{-1}$ can be unambiguously interpreted to arise due to ligand field transition of the octahedral component of the Co^{II} complex and may be assigned to transition ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ in an approximately octahedral field. The band at $24\,400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be attributed to charge transfer.

The magnetic moment of the Mn^{II} complex is 5.89 B.M. Its electronic spectrum shows band at $\sim 18\,000$, $25\,100$ and $27\,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggesting an octahedral geometry around the central metal ion and may be attributed to transition ${}^6A_{1g}(S) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, $\rightarrow {}^4E_g + {}^4A_{1g}(G)$ and $\rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(D)$ respectively. This is in accordance with the earlier reported values for Mn^{II} ion⁶.

The room temperature magnetic moment value of the VO^{II} complex (0.513 B.M.) is abnormally lower than the spin-only value (1.73 B.M.), which may be due to the presence of exchange coupled antiferromagnetism. The VO^{II} complex exhibits three bands at $\sim 12\,200$, $15\,600$ and $22\,700\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which may be assigned to $e_g \rightarrow b_{2g}$, $e_g \rightarrow a_{1g}$ and $e_g \rightarrow b_{1g}$ transitions respectively. These transitions are based on octahedral symmetry with tetragonal distortion, the elongation being on Z-axis⁷.

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Neutral Complexes of Platinum(II) and Palladium(II) with 2,2'-Dipyridylamine and 2,2'-Dipyridylketone

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CONSIDERABLE interest has recently been evinced in the complexes of platinum and palladium, mainly due to their possible utilisation as potential

anticancer drugs¹. In persuasion to our work in this area²⁻⁴, we report herein the complexes of 2,2'-dipyridylamine and 2,2'-dipyridylketone with platinum(II) and palladium(II).

Experimental

K_2PtCl_4 , K_2PdCl_4 , 2,2'-dipyridylamine (dpa) and 2,2'-dipyridylketone (dpk) (Aldrich) were used as such. All other chemicals were of reagent grade. Solvents were purified and dried prior to use.

Complexes $[\text{M}(\text{dpa})/(\text{dpk})\text{X}_2]$ were prepared by adding concentrated methanolic solution of dpa/dpk (1 mmol) to an aqueous solution (20 ml) of $\text{K}_2\text{PtCl}_4/\text{K}_2\text{PdCl}_4$ (1 mmol) excess of KX ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$, Br^- , or I^-) with vigorous stirring⁵. The complexes (precipitated immediately or after several hours) were washed successively with water, methanol and acetone, recrystallised from 1:1 DMF-water mixture and dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous calcium chloride, (60–90%).

Complexes $[\text{M}(\text{dpa}/\text{dpk})(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)]$ were prepared^{6,7} by adding concentrated methanolic solution of dpa/dpk (1 mmol) to an aqueous solution (20 ml) of $\text{K}_2\text{M}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The resulting solution was stirred for 24 h and its pH was maintained slightly acidic. The resulting solid was washed with water and dry ether, and dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous calcium chloride, (~50%).

The details of physical and spectroscopic measurements of the compounds were similar to those described earlier²⁻⁴.

Results and Discussion

Analytical data of the complexes are given in Table 1. All the complexes are insoluble in water and other common solvents, however, they are appreciably soluble in coordinating solvents such as DMF and DMSO. The molar conductances of the complexes in DMF solutions, range from 3 to $21\ \Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$, indicating their non-electrolytic nature⁸. All the complexes are diamagnetic in nature, as expected, indicating square-planar configuration.

The electronic absorption spectra of 2,2'-dipyridyl ketone complexes exhibit bands at 34.7–36.5 (broad, $\epsilon = 0.9 - 1.1 \times 10^4$) and 28–29.4 kK ($\epsilon = 0.13 - 0.16 \times 10^4\text{ dm}^3\text{ mol}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$). These bands can be tentatively assigned to $\pi-\pi^*$ transitions of the ligand and metal to ligand charge transfer (MLCT) transition respectively. In case of the 2,2'-dipyridylamine complexes $\pi-\pi^*$ transition bands appear at 36.8–37.2 ($\epsilon = 1.1 - 1.3 \times 10^4$) and 33.8–24.1 kK ($\epsilon = 1.2 - 1.4 \times 10^4\text{ dm}^3\text{ mol}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$) while MLCT band appears at 28.5–29.1 kK ($\epsilon = 0.3 - 0.46 \times 10^4\text{ dm}^3\text{ mol}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$). A weak band assignable to singlet to triplet transition is also observed at 24–25 kK in these complexes⁹.

The ir spectra (KBr) complexes were recorded in the range $4\,000 - 200\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ band at

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